

Analyzing bio-chemical samples using EPR spectroscopy

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1 Abstract

EPR spectroscopy is a very powerful bio-physical technique used by scientists over the years to look for free radicals within compounds. These free radicals take part in various organic and inorganic reactions and detecting them are crucial in a wide variety of research applications. Furthermore with the help of EPR spectroscopy, valuable structural and dynamical information of a wide variety of biological systems can be obtained. Therefore, this paper serves as an experimental and theoretical introduction to the file of EPR spectroscopy. Over the course of this paper, five different bio-chemical samples were tested on a Varian X-Band spectrometer, with the purpose of predicting the g -values of these compounds which help us detect not only the free radicals present, but also to decode the chemical structure of the given sample.

Keywords: Electron Paramagnetic Resonance, Lande's g -factor, Nuclear spin, Paramagnetic ions, Spectroscopy.

2 Introduction

Electron Paramagnetic Resonance (EPR) spectroscopy is an experimental technique used to examine and analyze information regarding various chemical species that essentially have unpaired electrons such as free radicals and transition metal ions. EPR is thus a very important technique because it discloses a lot of information regarding the paramagnetic ions in the sample such as:

- The spin state of ions
- The nature of ligands that surround the chemical sample

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- The interactions of the ions with the lattice

The structure, dynamics, and interactions of inherently disordered proteins like alpha-synuclein can be studied using electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy in combination with site-directed spin labelling. Electron spins pervade research and have an impact on a variety of chemical processes: they underpin transition metal chemistry and biochemistry, mediate photosynthesis and photovoltaics, and are crucial in quantum information, to mention a few. Unpaired electrons are detected by EPR spectroscopy, which offers precise information on the structure and bonding of paramagnetic species.

In this experimental procedure, a variety of paramagnetic samples were tested using EPR spectroscopy. The EPR readings observed are then used to analyze information and calculate the spin states and the g -factor (Lande's g -factor) of the unpaired electrons present in the paramagnetic sample. The g -factor is essentially the ratio of the electron's magnetic dipole moment to its angular momentum. The value of the g -factor varies according to the orientations of the molecule in an external magnetic field.

Therefore, for the following set of experiments the calculation of the g -factor is extremely necessary to critically understand the electronic structure of the given paramagnetic ion sample.

3 Background EPR theory

The EPR technique is essentially based on the interaction between the external magnetic field (B) and the spin magnetic moment (μ) of the unpaired electrons present in the sample. In the absence of any magnetic field, all the electrons have the same energy state and therefore, are in their degenerate state.

Figure 1: **The Zeeman effect, where in the presence of magnetic field a split in energy level is observed**

As an when an external magnetic field is applied, there is a split in the degenerate energy levels (*Zeeman effect*) due to the interaction of magnetic field

with the magnetic moment. Due to this split the electrons take two separate energy levels i.e. $+\frac{1}{2}g\mu B$ and $-\frac{1}{2}g\mu B$, where g represents the g -factor, μ represents the Bohr magneton and B represents the magnetic field.

Meanwhile as the magnetic field (B) is increased (Magnetic field in this case normally lies between 0 to 1T), microwave frequencies of certain energies ($h\nu$) are constantly being emitted. But the electron can only absorb the energy and go to the excited spin state only when the resonance condition is fulfilled.

The resonance condition is as followed:

$$h\nu = \delta E = g\mu B \quad (1)$$

Where h is the Planck's constant, ν is the frequency of the electromagnetic radiation emitted. Only when the above condition is agreed the electron can absorb the energy from the radiation and go to a higher energy spin state as shown in **Figure 1**.

In a typical EPR setup, a klystron is used to produce the microwave frequencies (in GHz). Upon absorbing the radiation at the resonance condition, a bell-shaped curve is observed as the absorption spectrum (**Figure 2**), representing the frequency interval at which energy is absorbed and released.

Figure 2: **An ESR absorption spectrum with spin $+\frac{1}{2}$ system**

Based on the given reading the g -factor as previously discussed can be calculated using the following relation:

$$g = 0.71449 \frac{\nu(\text{GHz})}{B(\text{kG})} \quad (2)$$

For a free radical the g -value lies approximately around 2.002. If the g -value deviates from the given value, it's concluded that the electron is in a bounded state with respect to an atom.

Often in many cases, transition series ions have nuclei with spin(I), interact with the unpaired electron and produces hyper-fine splitting in the EPR

spectra. This kind of interactions cause hyper-fine structures. If a nucleus with spin I interacts with an electron of spin S , the multiplicity for the hyper-fine splitting is given as $2I + 1$.

The hyper-fine splitting as discussed above is represented in **Figure 3**, where in A represents the hyper-fine constant and it's the characteristic of a particular ion. In the figure a sample with a hyperfine multiplicity of 3 can be observed, based on which the nuclear spin(I) can be calculated to be $I = \frac{3}{2}$.

Figure 3: A typical hyper-fine spectrum of a species with $I = \frac{3}{2}$

4 Experimental procedure

For the set of experiments done for the purpose of this paper, a Varian E-3 X-band spectrometer with a liquid nitrogen flow cryostat was used. The frequency range of the spectrometer lies from 8.5-12 GHz and the temperature range lies from 80K to room temperature.

As portrayed in **Figure 4**, the spectrometer uses a Klystron to provide the microwave energy to be absorbed by the electron. The sample to be observed is placed inside the resonant cavity area. The resonant cavity is placed inside an electromagnet. As the instrumentation is switched to 'OPERATE' mode, microwave power of constant frequency is produced by the Klystron and it travels down to the resonant cavity through a series of wave guides. Initially no microwave is absorbed but upon sweeping the magnetic field through the resonance, energy is absorbed by the sample in cavity.

Upon resonance the absorption signal is reflected from the resonance cavity to the detector and further to the electronics console for processing. This signal will then be plotted on X-Y plotter and analyzed.

In the given spectrometer, a liquid nitrogen flow cryostat is also attached to the resonant cavity, to cool down the sample and conduct low temperature

Figure 4: Schematic representation of the ESR spectrometer

EPR spectroscopy.

The samples used for experimentation are as follows:

DPPH- A small amount of grease was taken and placed inside a clean EPR tube and a sample of **DPPH** was placed inside the grease spot. EPR measurements were carried out at 300K with a Varian E-3 X-band spectrometer

Myoglobin- 3 samples of Myoglobin with different solvents were taken in the course of the following experiments. These are as follows :

1. **Dry myoglobin**- A dry sample of myoglobin was taken in an EPR tube to be tested under room temperature conditions.
2. **Myoglobin in H_2O** - A sample of myoglobin with water as a solvent was taken in an EPR tube. EPR measurements were carried out at a temperature of 117K.
3. **Myoglobin in glycerol** - A sample of myoglobin with glycerol as a solvent was placed in an EPR tube and measurements were carried out at a temperature of 110K.

Manganese Chloride in H_2O - A sample of $MnCl_2$ was taken in an EPR tube and measurements were carried out at 104K.

5 Results and discussions

Figure 5: **EPR absorption spectrum of DPPH. Experimental parameters are as follows: Temp-300K, Microwave frequency –9.139 GHz, Microwave power – 1.25mW, Modulation frequency - 100kHz**

DPPH- The obtained EPR spectrum of DPPH as shown in **Figure 5**, predicts that $g = 1.98$ in the case of DPPH when measured at a temperature of 300K . However, the theoretical g -value of DPPH is calculated to be **2.00**. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a presence of instrumental error within the experimentation. The error percent is calculated to be **1%**. As the experimental error percent is small, therefore we can conclude that DPPH is a free radical.

Manganese Chloride in H_2O - The EPR spectrum obtained from the sample of $MnCl_2$ predicts a g -value of **2.92** thus, proving that the unpaired electrons of the free radical $(Mn)^{2+}$ is in a bounded state within the compound $MnCl_2$. The ESR spectra also reveals a hyper-fine structure with a multiplicity level of 6 as observed in **Figure 6**. As a result of 6 hyper-fine structures present within the spectrum, it can be predicted using the $(2I + 1)$ relation that $(Mn)^{2+}$ has a nuclear spin(I) of **2.5**.

Myoglobin - As mentioned previously, 3 samples of myoglobin under different solvents were tested under EPR spectroscopy. The samples of both dry Mb and Mb in water revealed multiple g values in the system. In all the three samples the value of g never equates to $g = 2.00$ thus revealing that myoglobin isn't a free radical but instead it has a metal ion at it's base.

Figure 6: **EPR absorption spectrum of $MnCl_2$ in H_2O .** Experimental parameters are as follows: T-104K, Microwave power-5mW, Microwave frequency-9.144 GHz, Modulation frequency- 100kHz, Modulation field- 40G

Figure 7: **EPR spectrum of dry Mb.** Experimental parameters are as follows: Microwave power- 5mW, Microwave frequency- 9.146 GHz, Modulation field- 20G, Modulation frequency-100kHz

In the case of dry Myoglobin (Mb) three different signals were observed (as shown in **Figure 7**). The g values which were observed are $g_1 = 2.5$, $g_2 = 2.17$ and $g_3 = 1.92$. Based on the observations it can be predicted that these multiple g values arise from the low spin Fe^{3+} ion present in the active site of the dry myoglobin sample. In the case Mb in glycerol a simple bell shaped absorption graph was observed and a g -value of 2.17 was recorded as shown in **figure 8**.

Meanwhile in the case of Mb in H_2O , multiple EPR signals were recorded. Upon analyzing the signals, a pair of high spin Fe^{3+} along with low Fe^{3+} sig-

Figure 8: EPR spectrum of Mb of glycerol. Experimental parameters: T-110K, Microwave frequency - 9.122GHz, Microwave power-25mW, Modulation field- 40G, Modulation frequency - 100kHz

Figure 9: EPR spectrum of Mb in H_2O , Experimental parameters: T- 117K, Microwave frequency-9.12 GHz, Microwave power- 25mW, Modulation field- 40G , Modulation frequency-100kHz

nals were observed (the g values for which are summarized in **Figure 9** and **Table 1**). Upon comparing the readings of Mb sample under different solvents, it can be concluded that the solvent plays a crucial role in altering the readings of the sample. This shift in readings of the EPR signals and the g values can be explained by two major chemical phenomena.

The major reason behind this is due to the nature of the two solvents. Both the solvents under low temperatures cool in a different manner. As, both the samples freeze in different ways, the geometry of the ligand around the Fe^{3+} ion gets affected, due to which there is a change in the signal observed. As a

result of this (as shown in **Figure 8**) in the glycerol samples , the EPR signals broaden up to form a broad EPR line.

Another possible explanation for the change in readings can explained with context to the specific heat capacities of both the solvents. H_2O has a higher specific heat than glycerol due to which a change in absorption spectrum and further a change of g value is observed. Due to this high specific heat of H_2O , the sample under water cools slower than glycerol due to which there exists a thermal energy difference. Based on the thermal energy difference, a change in reading is also observed.

6 Conclusion

Data collected from various EPR spectra were used to study various bio-chemical samples and the effect that solvent has on the EPR spectra of a compound. The g value for each sample was calculated (as shown in **Table 1**). DPPH as expected resembled the characteristics of a free radical.

Meanwhile $MnCl_2$ displayed a hyper-fine structure of level 6, as a result of its nuclear spin. The nuclear spin was later calculated to obtain a value of $I = 2.5$.

In the case of Myoglobin, three different spectra were obtained for different solvent conditions. For dry Myoglobin, three g -values were observed a result of the Fe^{3+} ion present at the active site of Myoglobin. Further the change in readings in the case of Mb under different solvents was predicted to be due to the nature of cooling of the solvents , which further affects ligand geometry.

Therefore, over the the given set of results and observations, it can be concluded that EPR spectroscopy is a very powerful experimental technique, offering us a great deal of insight into any kind of paramagnetic sample using the calculated g -factor of the sample.

Sample	Spectrum details
DPPH	$g = 2.17$
$MnCl_2$	h.s: 6 splittings spaced at, $A=109.65$ G, centred on $g=2.92$
Dry Mb	l.s axial: $g_x = 2.5, g_y = 2.17, g_z = 1.92$
Mb in water	h.s axial: $g_1 = 6.00, g_2 = 2.01$ and l.s: $g_3 = 2.4, g_4 = 1.97$
Mb in glycerol	$g=2.17$ and $\delta B = 672.6$ G

Table 1: **Summary of obtained EPR results.** All spectroscopic measurements of samples were recorded on a Varian E-3 X-band EPR spectrometer equipped with liquid nitrogen cryostat. High spin and low spin have been abbreviated to h.s and l.s respectively. A represents the hyper fine coupling constant measured for Mn^{2+} ion.

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8 References

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